

Speculation on the Statistical Enhancement Factor For Bosons

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In a previous note (1), we argued that even though photons and particles with rest mass both have the same quantum free particle probability (wavefunction) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, they have different spins, spin 1 (photon) and spin $\frac{1}{2}$ (fermion like nucleons, electron). We argued that one may find equations for spin matrices by identifying an inherent force associated with the object. For a particle with rest mass, we argued that one chooses rest mass, m_0 , which is proportional to the force, inertia. For a photon, one chooses the electric field. The key is then to find an equation which is linear in the inherent force and contains p , E (for special relativistic effects and geometry). For a particle with rest mass, the Lorentz invariant $-EE + cc p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0 c^4$ is linearized as Dirac showed. For a photon, one seeks an equation linear in the electric field. One may linearize $d/dt \text{ partial } (.5e_0 E \cdot E + .5/u_0 B \cdot B) + 1/u_0 \text{ grad } \cdot (E \times B) = 0$, where E =electric field and B =magnetic field.

For a particle with rest mass, one must retain the identity of the rest mass when forces interact. If one has two identical m_0 's with the same center-of-mass, one must somehow distinguish between the two to deliver an impulse hit to only one. This may be done by using a magnetic field and having one particle have spin up, and the other, spin down. This leads to the Pauli exclusion principle. Using the Pauli exclusion principle in a two body elastic scattering problem, one may easily establish time reversal balance by:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) \{1-p(e_3)\}\{1-p(e_4)\} = p(e_3)p(e_4) \{1-p(e_1)\}\{1-p(e_2)\} \quad ((1)).$$

From this one may obtain the Fermi-Dirac distribution. The question becomes: What does one do for photons?

We argue that photons do not interact in the same manner as two particles with rest mass which elastically scatter. Instead we consider photons interacting with electrons in atoms. We note that in the case of particles with rest mass, there is a grouping of two energies, i.e. e_1, e_2 on the LHS side of ((1)), and e_3, e_4 , on the RHS. We keep this notion of grouping, but note that e_1 , and e_2 are not being converted into e_3, e_4 photons. Rather, all four types of photons are present and may interact with the electrons in atoms. Thus, we consider the sum of the probabilities for the e_1, e_2 grouping, namely $(e_1, e_2) + (e_1, e_2) e_3 + (e_1, e_2) e_4 + (e_1, e_2) e_3, e_4$. We argue that the sum of probabilities for this set of groupings should equal the sum of probabilities for the grouping of (e_3, e_4) , i.e. $(e_3, e_4) + (e_3, e_4) e_1 + (e_3, e_4) e_2 + (e_3, e_4) e_1, e_2$. This is equivalent to: $p(e_1)p(e_2) \{1+p(e_3)\}\{1+p(e_4)\} = p(e_3)p(e_4) \{1+p(e_1)\}\{1+p(e_2)\}$. From this, the Bose-Einstein distribution follows.

General Notion of Spin and Its Effect on Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Distributions

The notion of fermions and bosons seems to be linked to spin, with fermions having half-integer spin and bosons, integer. We restrict ourselves to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ for fermions (and consider particles with rest mass) and spin 1 and photons for bosons. In a previous note (1), we tried to show how spin arises by arguing that it is directly linked to the notion of an inherent force. In the

case of a particle with rest mass m_0 , we argue that the inherent force is inertia, proportional to m_0 , and in the case of a photon, it is the electric field (linked to the B magnetic field as well). In such a case, we argue in (1) that to find spin matrices, one must seek an equation linear in the inherent force.

For a particle with rest mass, one may linearize $-EE + cc \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0 c^2$ as m_0 is proportional to the inherent force. This leads to Dirac's spin $\frac{1}{2}$ situation. For a photon, one may linearize:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5e_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

where \mathbf{E} =electric field and \mathbf{B} =magnetic field. This yields ϵ_{ijk} (Levi-Civita symbol) as the spin-1 matrices, with i identifying the matrix and jk , its elements.

One may ask: This explains how to obtain spin, but how does this pertain to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions?

In the case of the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ fermion, if one has two m_0 rest mass particles, one must be able to render a force to one or the other in order to demonstrate that there are two particles and not a single $2m_0$. If the two m_0 masses have their center-of-masses coincide, there is no way to distinguish and render a force knowingly to one or the other. If, however, they have different spin projections, they would interact differently in a magnetic field and could be distinguished. Thus, we argue that if all quantum numbers except spin projection are the same for two particles with rest m_0 , one must have one with spin up and the other with spin down, creating an antisymmetric wavefunction which becomes 0 if one tries to set the 1,2 particle labels the same. As a result, force/interaction is the key idea linked to imposing the Pauli principle, we argued in (1).

In terms of reaction time reversal balance, one may use ensemble averages and write:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) \{1-p(e_3)\}\{1-p(e_4)\} = p(e_3)p(e_4) \{1-p(e_1)\}\{1-p(e_2)\} \quad ((3))$$

This leads to the Fermi-Dirac distribution:

$$\ln(p(e_i) / \{1-p(e_i)\}) = -(e_i - u) / T \quad ((4))$$

As a result, understanding the interactions which occur in the rest mass m_0 (inherent force) case seem to lead to the Fermi-Dirac distribution. In the next section, we try to find the appropriate interactions which occur in the photon case and obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution.

Photons and the Bose-Einstein Case

Given that photon electric fields add, and that the electric field is the inherent force, there is no requirement to distinguish between one piece of electric field from one photon with the piece from the second photon. Thus, there is no Pauli exclusion principle, but one does not

immediately have an equation like ((3)) we argue. One must find reasons for creating one and we argue that the key reason is considering the appropriate interaction associated with photons. Unlike particles with rest mass, one does not have a photon with e_1 elastically scattering with one with e_2 to create e_3, e_4 . Instead, we argue that photons interact with electrons in atoms, which means that if one considers a kind of balance like ((3)) for e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4 one must consider that all four types of photons are present at the same time and interact with electrons in atoms. One may, however, consider grouping e_1 and e_2 together for the LHS of an equation (like e_1, e_2 are grouped for an elastic collision) and equating this to a grouping of e_3, e_4 on the RHS. We suggest that the sum of probabilities for all possible photon interactions with the atoms with the restriction of the groupings leads to:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_3) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_4) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_3)p(e_4) \\ = p(e_3)p(e_4) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_1) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_2) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_1)p(e_2) \quad ((5))$$

This in turn, may be written as:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) \{1+p(e_3)\}\{1+p(e_4)\} = p(e_3)p(e_4) \{1+p(e_1)\}\{1+p(e_2)\} \quad ((6))$$

This equation holds together with $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ ((7)). This leads to:

$$\ln(p(e_i) / (1+p(e_i))) = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((7))$$

((7)) yields the Bose-Einstein distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that spin follows the notion of intrinsic force as developed in (1). For a particle with rest mass, intrinsic force is inertia (or rest mass). If one has two identical particles with the same center-of-mass, how does one render a force to one and not the other to distinguish between the two and show that one does not have a single particle with rest mass $2m_0$. We suggest that one may do so using a magnetic field if one particle is spin up and the other spin down. If this is not the case, then one cannot distinguish between the two and this is unphysical. This leads to Pauli's exclusion principle and an antisymmetric spin wavefunction. If one applies the Pauli principle to reaction balance for an ensemble average, one has: $p(e_1)p(e_2)(1-p(e_3))(1-p(e_4)) = p(e_3)p(e_4)(1-p(e_1))(1-p(e_2))$ which yields the Fermi-Dirac principle.

For a photon, the electric field is the inherent force, we argue, and one does not distinguish between different pieces of electric field, but has a resultant vector. Thus, Pauli's principle does not apply. We suggest that in order to analyze photons, one cannot think of a two body elastic interaction. Rather, photons interact with electrons in atoms. We suggest that one may consider grouping (e_1, e_2) together, but that e_3 and e_4 photons are still present. Thus, we consider (e_1, e_2) as a unit exciting electrons as well as any other combination of e_3, e_4 photons because all four types of photons are present. We suggest that the sum of probabilities should match the

sum of probabilities for an (e_3, e_4) grouping with e_1, e_2 photons present. This leads to:
 $p(e_1)p(e_2) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_3) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_4) + p(e_1)p(e_2)p(e_3)p(e_4) = p(e_3)p(e_4) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_1) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_2) + p(e_3)p(e_4)p(e_1)p(e_2)$. This may be rewritten as:
 $p(e_1)p(e_2)(1+p(e_3))(1+p(e_4)) = p(e_3)p(e_4)(1+p(e_1))(1+p(e_2))$ which yields the Bose-Einstein distribution.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Spin and the Pauli Exclusion Principle (preprint, zenodo, 2026)